

Written Hall Exam (Spring 2019)

Data Structures and Algorithms

Question 1 (20 points) (Each sub-question is 2 points) Answer the following questions.

1.1. Assume that you have an algorithm with $O(N^2)$ time complexity. It takes 0.5 milliseconds for this algorithm to execute for input size of 100 on computer A. What would be the execution time if the same algorithm is executed for input size 200 on computer B that is 2 times slower than computer A (Assume that low order terms are negligible)

- a. 2 milliseconds
- b. 4 milliseconds
- c. 8 milliseconds
- d. 5 milliseconds

1.2. Which of the following functions does not belong to $O(N \log N)$ complexity class?

- a. N
- b. \sqrt{N}
- c. $N \log^2 N$
- d. $N \log N^2$

1.3. Suppose we are supposed to write a program that takes Strings entered per line as input and terminates when an empty line is entered as input (i.e., the program does not know how many strings will be entered in advance). Which of the following would result in a fast program that does not waste space in memory?

- a. Use String array and increase array size one cell at a time for addition of each String to the array.
- b. Use String array and increase array by 100 cells whenever the array gets full to add the remaining strings one by one. Once all strings are stored resize the array if there are any unused cells.
- c. Use ArrayList class in `java.util`. After addition of each string to the ArrayList, use the `trim` method to resize the array.
- d. Use ArrayList class in `java.util`. After addition of all strings to the ArrayList, use the `trim` method to resize the array.

1.4. If you are using an array to implement a stack, then what would be the worst-case time complexity of push operation?

- a. $O(1)$
- b. $O(N)$
- c. $O(\log N)$
- d. $O(N^2)$

1.5. What will be printed by the following code, assuming that Queue implements a queue of integers?

```
Queue q = new Queue();
q.enqueue(3);
q.enqueue(2);
System.out.println(q.dequeue());
q.enqueue(4);
System.out.println(q.dequeue());
```

- a. 3, 2
- b. Nothing will be printed, the system will crash
- c. 3, 4
- d. 2, 4

1.6. Which of the following operations is not supported by hash tables?

- a. Insert (i.e., inserting an item)
- b. findMin (i.e., finding the item with minimum key value)
- c. find (i.e., finding an item)
- d. delete (i.e., deleting an item)

1.7. Suppose you are going to implement a music playlist such as those in Spotify or iTunes. Music playlist is supposed to allow you to skip songs in backwards and forward direction, play the next track, add a new track to the playlist as well as allowing to jump to the beginning and end of a playlist. Which of the following data structures or Abstract Data Types (ADT) would you use to implement this music playlist?

- a. Tree
- b. Stack
- c. Singly linked List
- d. Doubly Linked List

1.8. Which of the following is true about hash tables?

- a. You can always place a new item in a quadratic probing hash table.

- b. You can always place a new item in a quadratic probing hash table if the load factor never exceeds 0.5
- c. You can always place a new item in a quadratic probing hash table if the load factor never exceeds 0.5 and table size is a prime number.
- d. You can always place a new item in a linear probing hash table if the load factor never exceeds 0.5 and table size is a prime number.

1.9. How many edges does a tree with N nodes have ?

- a. N
- b. $N - 1$
- c. $\log N$
- d. $2N$

1.10. Assume that you have 10 integers, which are almost sorted in ascending order and most of these integers are identical. Which of the following sorting algorithms would you choose to sort these integers (i.e., would have the least Big-O time complexity)?

- a. Bubble sort (non-optimized version)
- b. Mergesort
- c. Quicksort (pivot is the middle element in the array $(\text{low} + \text{high})/2$)
- d. Insertion sort

Question 2 (10 points) Calculate the big-O time complexities of the following 5 functions (For a correct answer to each function, you get **2 points**).

```
int function1(int n) {
    int sum = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < n; i++)
        sum ++;
    for (int j = 1; j < n; j++)
        sum ++;
    return sum; }
-----

int function2(int n) {
    int sum = 0;
    for (int i = 1; i < n; i = i*2)
        sum ++;
    return sum;}
-----

int function3(int n) {
    if (n == 0)
        return 0;
    else
        return function3(n-1) + function3(n-1);}
-----

int function4(int n) {
    for (int i = 0; i < n; i++)
        for (int j = 0; j < n; j++)
            for (int k = 1; k < n; k = k*2)
                sum ++;}
```

```

-----
int function5(int n) {
    int sum = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < n; i++)
        sum ++;
    if (n > 1)
        return sum + 3*function5(n/2);
    else
        return 0; }

```

Question 3 (10 points) Below is a smaller version of the Java class you implemented for doubly linked lists during Hands-on Programming Session #6. Make the necessary changes on the code so that the code piece below becomes a Java class for singly linked lists. (You can simply make the changes on the code itself).

```

class DoublyLinkedList<Item> {

    private int size = 0;
    private Node<Item> head;
    private Node<Item> tail;

    private static class Node<Item> {

        Node<Item> next = null;
        Item el = null;
        Node<Item> prev = null;

    }

    public DoublyLinkedList() {
        head = new Node<>();
        tail = new Node<>();
        head.next = tail;
        tail.prev = head;
    }

    public void reverse() {
        Node<Item> temp = head;
        head = tail;
        tail = temp;

        Node<Item> current = head;
        while (current != null) {
            temp = current.next;
            current.next = current.prev;
            current.prev = temp;
            current = current.next;
        }
    }
}

```

Question 4 (11 points) Sort the sequence 12, 10, 4, 26, 17, 2, 5 by using Quicksort algorithm. Firstly, select a strategy to pick the pivot. Briefly explain why you would select that pivot picking strategy? (3 points) Then, sort sequence showing the steps. During sorting, when array size becomes equal to or less than 3, use insertion sort to sort those short sequences, showing the steps for insertion sort. (8 points)

Question 5 (10 points) Below there is the summary of a benchmark study for sorting algorithms. Examine the table below and answer the following questions (Each question is 2 points):

- Which algorithm performs worst under all conditions? Why?
- Insertion sort performs best for short arrays. Explain, why.
- Complexity of mergesort is $O(N \log N)$ and complexity of insertion sort is $O(N^2)$. Still, insertion sort performs better for short arrays. Please explain why?
- Why is performance of quicksort with pivot being the first element of the array worse than that of mergesort?
- When pivot is randomly sampled, still quicksort does not perform as good as mergesort. Do you think performance of quicksort can be improved? Why or why not?

BENCHMARK SUMMARY		Execution Time (CPU seconds)	
		Sorted (ascending order)	Sorted (descending order)
bubble sort (non-optimized)	array size: 100	0.000087	0.000213
	array size: 10,000	0.119410	0.187599
merge sort	array size: 100	0.000021	0.000040
	array size: 10,000	0.000039	0.000054
insertion sort	array size: 100	0.000014	0.000036
	array size: 10,000	0.011634	0.034459
Quicksort (pivot: randomly sampled)	array size: 100	0.000040	0.000056
	array size: 10,000	0.000039	0.000059
Quicksort (pivot: A[0])	array size: 100	0.000048	0.000096
	array size: 10,000	0.001837	0.005395

Question 6 (14 points) Show the resulting tree T_1 that you construct by inserting 6, 4, 1, 11, 9, 13, 5 in an initially empty binary search tree (BST). Then do the following steps (Each step is 2 points):

- 1) Delete the root of the binary search tree (BST) T_1 and show the resulting BST T_2
- 2) Delete node with value "11" from BST T_2 and show the resulting BST T_3
- 3) Delete node with value "4" from BST T_3 and show the resulting BST T_4
- 4) Write down the sequence of the values of nodes of BST T_4 using pre-order tree traversal

- 5) Write down the sequence of the values nodes of BST T_4 using in-order tree traversal
- 6) Write down the sequence of the values nodes of BST T_4 using post-order tree traversal
- 7) Write down the sequence of the values of nodes of BST T_4 using level-order tree traversal (i.e., breadth first search)

Question 7 (10 points) Consider that an array of integers denotes the amount of money a person makes or loses in the stock market at certain points in time. You need to write the pseudocode or Java code that finds the maximum amount of net (i.e., cumulative) money a person makes within a certain time interval. The Big-O time complexity of your code should be $O(N \log N)$. If you write a correct algorithm with higher Big-O time complexity, you will get partial points (5 points)

For example, consider the following array:

```
int [] A = {20000, 50000, -10000, 70000, -30000, 5000, -190000};
```

Each element in the array A is amount of money a person loses or makes in SEK (negative values mean that person loses money) at a certain time. For every $i < j$, the amount of money made or lost at $A[i]$ belongs to an earlier time than the amount of money made or lost at $A[j]$. For instance, for the above array maximum amount of net (i.e, cumulative) money a person makes in the stock market during the entire time (i.e., $0 \leq i \leq 6$) is 130,000 SEK and this money is made during the sub-period from time $i = 0$ until $i = 3$ (including $i = 3$).

Question 8 (15 points) A text editor works only by adding and deleting lines of text. There are no commands to alter a line in the text. You can execute the following commands in this text editor.

- command “i” in the text editor puts the editor itself in input mode. All text that is input following command “i”, is added to the stored text in editor after the insertion sign (i.e., “>”). All text input is added to stored text, until a line, which consists of only the full stop sign (i.e., “.”), is entered as input. Full stop sign (i.e., “.”) causes the editor to go back to the command mode, with the insertion sign (i.e., “>”) being in front of the last line of the entered text (Insertion sign “>” indicates the line before which a text can be inserted).
- command “+” move the insertion sign (i.e., “>”) one line up the stored text.
- command “-“ move the insertion sign (i.e., “>”) one line down the stored text.
- command “p“ prints the line, which is after the current insertion point without moving the insertion sign (i.e., “>”).
- command “d“ deletes the line, which is after the current insertion sign “>” and insertion sign points the line that was before the deleted line.
- command “l“ prints the entire text showing the location of the insertion sign (i.e., “>”).

Below is an example output that can be obtained by entering the commands above:

```
: i
This is an implementation of a text editor.
Implementation uses a data structure.
Data structure used allows the commands to be executed efficiently.
.
: d
Implementation uses a data structure.
: -
This is an implementation of a text editor.
```

```
: +
Implementation uses a data structure.
: p
Implementation uses a data structure.
: l
  This is an implementation of a text editor.
> Implementation uses a data structure.
```

Please answer the following for Question 8:

(If you need, source code of text editor is in Appendix A)

8.1) How would you implement the text editor above using doubly linked lists? Explain by using sketches and pseudocode how you would implement methods to insert a line (i.e., `insert(Object obj)`), to delete a line (i.e., `delete()`), to move the insertion sign “>” one line up in the text (i.e., `backward()`) and one line down the text (i.e., `forward()`). (7 points).

8.2) What would be the Big-O time complexities for each of the following methods, `insert(Object obj)`, `delete()`, `forward()` and `backward()` (4 points).

8.3) In order to implement the basic operations for the commands of the text editor, if `ArrayList` were used instead of doubly linked list, then what would be the Big-O time complexity of for each of the following methods, `insert(Object obj)`, `delete()`, `forward()` and `backward()` (4 points).

Question 9 (BONUS: 30 points) The similarity of two documents (each with distinct words) is defined to be the size of the intersection divided by the size of the union. For example, if the documents consist of integers, the similarity of {1, 5, 3} and {1, 7, 2, 3} is 0.4., because intersection has size 2 and union has size 5.

We have a long list of documents (with distinct values each associated with an ID) where similarity is believed to be “sparse”. That is, any two arbitrarily selected documents are very likely to have similarity 0. Design an algorithm that returns a list of pairs of document IDs and the associated similarity. In order to get full points (i.e., 30 points) you need to design an algorithm that has equal to or more improved big-O time complexity than $O(D^2W)$. (D is the total number of documents and W is the number of words in each document). You can get partial points for designing an algorithm with $O(D^2W + DW \log W)$ time complexity (20 points) and also for designing an algorithm with D^2W^2 time complexity (10 points). You can either write the pseudocode with sketches and explanations or the Java code for your algorithm.

Print only the pairs with similarity greater than 0. Empty documents should not be printed at all. For simplicity, assume each document is presented by an array of distinct integers.

EXAMPLE:

Input:

13: {14, 15, 100, 9, 3}

16: {32, 1, 9, 3, 5}

19: {15, 29, 2, 6, 8, 7}

24: {7, 10}

Output:

ID1, ID2: SIMILARITY

13, 19: 0.1

13, 16: 0.25

19, 24: 0.14

APPENDIX A: Source code of text editor in Question 8

```
import java.io.*;

public class TextEditor {
    public static void main(String[] args) throws IOException {
        BufferedReader in = new BufferedReader(new InputStreamReader(System.in));
        StacksWithLinkedList lines = new StacksWithLinkedList();
        char ch;
        String command, line;
        do {
            System.out.print(": ");
            command = in.readLine();
            ch = command.charAt(0);
            switch(ch) {
                case 'i':
                    do {
                        line = in.readLine();
                        if(line.length() == 1 && line.charAt(0) == '.')
                            break;
                        lines.insert(line);
                    } while(true);
                    break;
                case 'd':
                    if(lines.isEmpty())
                        System.out.println("?");
                    else {
                        lines.delete();
                        if(!lines.isEmpty())
                            System.out.println(lines.current());
                    }
                    break;
                case '+':
                    if(lines.isEmpty() || lines.atEnd())
                        System.out.println("?");
                    else {
                        lines.forward();
                        System.out.println(lines.current());
                    }
                    break;
                case '-':
                    if(lines.isEmpty() || lines.atStart())
                        System.out.println("?");
                    else {
                        lines.backward();
                        System.out.println(lines.current());
                    }
                    break;
            }
        } while(true);
    }
}
```

```
        }  
        break;  
    case 'p':  
        if(lines.isEmpty())  
            System.out.println("?");  
        else  
            System.out.println(lines.current());  
        break;  
    case 'l':  
        System.out.print(lines);  
        break;  
    case 'q': break;  
    default:  
        System.out.println("?"); }  
} while(ch != 'q');  
} }
```